

Employee's Behaviour and Work-Life Balance in Some Selected Broadcasting Firm in Ibadan

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Abstract

Work life balance is a very important phenomenon that is of great concern to various employees in both private and public sector. It goes beyond prioritizing the work role and one's personal life. The study focused on the effect of work life balance on employee's behaviour in some selected organizations in Ibadan. The research adopted the descriptive survey design. The study population is represented by 500 employees at Radio Nigeria in Oyo State. The study employed *Taro Yamane's* formula to select 220 sample size from the population size of 500. The study used questionnaire as research instrument and the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23.0. Findings showed that there is a significant influence of work life balance and job commitment and also there was no significant influence between work life balance and job satisfaction among employees. Based on the above findings, this study concludes that there are strategies put in place by organization to help foster effectiveness among employees at Radio Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that there is need for managers of these organizations to encourage their employees to fix their leave at their convenient period after performing all their work related duties. Employees should also make the very best use of their annual leave for their personal development and policies on welfare for families should be encouraged to care for dependent as well as the emergency unit.

Keywords: Employee behaviour, Job commitment, Job satisfaction, Work-life balance

Word Count: 241

Introduction

The articulation of work and life, cast as work-life balance, has become a key feature of much current government, practitioner and academic debate. It is believed that balancing a successful career with a personal or family life can be challenging and impact on a person's behavioural outcomes in their work and personal life's roles. Work-life balance is about effectively managing the juggling act between paid work and all other activities that are important to people such as family community activities, voluntary work, personal development and leisure and recreation. The ability to balance between workplace's needs and personal life's needs is perceived as an important issue among workers globally.

Inadequate work life balance is a problem that poses a big risk to workers well-being, their behaviour as well as the organizational performance. Many employees often have difficulties in attempting to balance employment responsibilities with their social life. On the other hand, family and work are the most important domains of life for most adults (Piotrkowski, 2019). Globally, the modern economy and the related social changes like technological advancement and increasing number of dual-earner families, has presented pressure on harmonizing personal, family and work life. Employees' behaviour toward these organizations and life are affected by work-life balance. Work-life balance is especially important when the organizations have to manage highly technical and professional jobs because their high commitment and loyalty is needed for the success of the organization. It is observed that changes in the work style, work culture, family needs, work demands in Organizations are rapidly taking place which eventually increased the population of dual earner couples, single parent families and eldercare responsibilities (Piotrkowski, 2019). These increased changes in most organization can have adverse impact on employees' behavioural outcome (their satisfaction towards their jobs, job involvement as well as employee's commitment) which is quite evident in the amount of backlog in the organization, poor attitude towards work and poor interpersonal relationships. Increased pressure at the workplace negatively affects the work-life balance and this determines the job outcome of employees.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of work life balance on employee's behaviour in some selected organizations in Ibadan.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the level of work behaviour among employees in the study organization
2. Examine the link between work life balance and employees behaviour (job commitment and job satisfaction) in the study organization.

Literature Review

Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance is essential for companies and workers in order to maintain optimum control of various activities at work, at home, and in personal life, as employees with a strong work-life balance contributed further to organizational performance and development. There has been an interest in psychology's work-life system, particularly in the origins and consequences of the recent years dispute between the realms of work-to-life and life-to-work. Work-life balance refers to the resource distribution and restrictions between the realm of job and non-work, as in family responsibilities or other personal responsibilities (Singh, 2018).

The WLB is concerned with maintaining influence of leisure and job hours. It is believed that the commonly confused WLB definition does not arise by mistake, but it happens on the basis of a well-organized strategy⁶. Balance of work life is the concept of finding an optimal balance between an individual's working life and his personal life and both of their connections. The level of significance assigned to this phenomenon these days is due to the negative consequences brought on by this phenomenon's extreme lack. Was Happiness Relative according to study paper? An effective work-life balance makes a person more content and happier. This contentment helps people to maintain and be satisfied with the level of hard work they put into their respective careers (Fitzpatrick, 2013).

Konrad and Mangel (2020) stated that the idea of work-life balance deals with discovering the ways in which an individual maintains equilibrium between conflicting work and home demands, i.e. how individuals do or can perform their job-related and personal obligations in such a way that an incompatible situation does not emerge.

Therefore, as it is a very broad field of study, scholars have tried to analyze it under different scopes, including knowledge systems, gender-based analysis paradigms, business administration, psychology, sociology, and especially in the area of human resource management. Most specifically, as technology has paved avenues for mode of work in telecommuting and freelancing, it has practically rendered numerous earlier hypotheses as unfounded in this field of human sciences. Additionally (like other subjects dealing closely with human activities), there is no universal definition of what constitutes or develops an employee's work-life balance practice and the term usually refers to either employer benefits, remote or flexible work options, overtime options, leaves and vacations, job sharing options, family health options for employees and o

The justification for endorsing these practices is commonly related to the assumption that

there is a correlation or partnership between work-life balance of an employee and organizational effectiveness and workplace dynamism (Estes & Michael, 2015).

Employee's Behaviour

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction explains how happy workers/employees are with their new job or the role employees are saddled with. Job reveals literature, a set of related concepts that characterize job satisfaction (Locke, 2007). The most famous is Locke's one, which identifies job satisfaction as a pleasurable or optimistic emotional response to the work experiences of an individual. Job satisfaction can be described as the aggregation of feelings and beliefs about a current job (Hill, 2010). It has also been view as a positive attitude that is assumed to contribute to good success, or as a representation of the feelings of an employee about different facets of work (Daft & Marcic, 2016; Stone, 2015). Observing job satisfaction, it is very necessary to remember two separate terms which are used similarly in literature, i.e. job satisfaction with regard only to the task itself or the key function of one's daily employment, and job satisfaction in general which involves a number of different elements, such as pay satisfaction, peers, management or working conditions.

Over the past several decades job satisfaction has been an area of interest to many researchers (Hackman & Oldhman, 2019). In fact one of the most studied topics of corporate psychology has been career satisfaction. The interest in job satisfaction stems from its relationship to the efficiencies and long-term success of an employee. Kornhauser (2015) noted that job satisfaction is directly related to the happiness of an individual, and that there is a positive relationship between work and satisfaction. Smith, Kendall and Hulin, (2019) described job satisfaction as "feelings or affective responses to (workplace) situational aspects". More recently, scholars have recognized that job satisfaction is a condition better characterized as possessing the character of both cognitive (thought) and affective (feelings). Brief & Weiss (2012) indicated that occupational impact studies should be used to assess employee satisfaction and that occupational affective experiences are often a source for job satisfaction.

Job Commitment

Whyte defined organizational commitment for the first time in 1956, as follows:"... white collar employees in large organizations live their lives dominated by the life and commitment of the company. White, Hill, McGowen, Mills and Sweaton (2013) opined that not only does a man in the organization work for the organization but he also commits to

the organization and feels as if such an employee belongs to it". It was also defined as a type of "commitment resulting from Becker's recognition of the cost or lost side bets associated with discontinuing his efforts or activities in the organization as well as other values such as time, position and money he had gained during his employment." Organizational engagement provides information on the level of commitment the employees feel towards their organizations (White et al., 2013).

What is now apparent is that, as long as the organization has been able to engage the right kind of employees and has provided an appropriate working environment, employee engagement will be largely influenced by the interactions between colleagues and with their immediate and senior managers. It should also be assumed that the relationship between the company and the employee is no different from any other form of partnership (Torrington, Hall & Taylor, 2015).

Commitment is dynamic and ongoing and allows workers to find opportunities to better their employees' working lives (Lawler, 2017). Commitment can literally be thought of in terms of feelings of obligation or emotional commitment. In recent years, though, there has been arisen increase in consensus that dedication should be regarded as a multidimensional concept. Employees who are committed to their jobs and organizations have positive attitudes and are willing to contribute ideas, are innovative and willing to go an extra mile in their contribution to the achievement of the organizational goals (Lawler, 2017).

Much of the time as these workers transfer, they relocate with the information and trade secrets gained by their previous employers to rival organisations, creating an even more precarious situation for the latter. Employees that switch every six years on average between employers. This condition requires that management should recognize the reasons why workers often change their jobs. After these factors have been established, managers may instead build continuity techniques to help retain important workers for a longer period (Abassi & Hollman, 2018).

Wikipedia (2009) outlines Meyer and Allen's three-component model of Commitment as follows:

Affective Commitment- Is a positive emotional attachment of the employee to the organization. This employee actively agrees with the company's priorities and wants to be a member of the enterprise. A participant is the employee if he / she 'wants to.'

Continuance Commitment – One commits to an organization because he / she perceives high costs of losing organizational membership including the economic costs (e.g. pension accruals) and social costs (friendship with co-workers) that would be incurred. A leader is the employee as he needs to.

Normative commitment-One commits to the organization because of sense of duty. These sentiments may be derived from many sources. For example this person who feels obligated to bring more work and continue to repay the 'debt' may have been invested by the company in preparation. This may also represent an internalized practice to be faithful to one's organization. The employee is sticking with the company because he/she has been working for it.

Theoretical Review

Border Theory

Five key frameworks (segmentation, spillover, reward, instrumental and conflict) have been used to analyze the interaction between work and non-work / family life. These frameworks have been criticized for being largely abstract, not emphasizing causes and effects and not having a context for the study of the distinctions between work and non-work (Guest, 2002). Clark has set forward Border Theory (BT) as a solution to this critique (Clark, 2000). According to Guest "Border Theory opens up a fertile stream of research concentrating on the essence of the realms of work and home, on the boundaries within such two spheres but also on the permeability of borders and the ease by which such boundaries may be handled or transferred "such that individuals may reach work-family unity (WFB) (Guest, 2002).

While the strength and permeability of boundaries and the central or peripheral presence of border crossers are significant in the BT work-family, Clark has given little knowledge about factors leading to these elements (Clark, 2000). For example, BT only addresses those variables (i.e., geographical, temporal and psychological aspects) that affect the intensity of the work-family boundary and its eventual permeability while empirical data indicates that influences at the organizational level (e.g. culture) may also contribute (Clark, 2001).

In addition, if one is a secondary or core work-based person, it can also be linked to organizational influences (e.g. community, workplace behaviors, leadership style) as well as human variables (e.g. life-phase) that have not yet been addressed in detail in BT (Lambert, Kass, Piotrowski & Vodanovich, 2006). BT conceptualizes work and family as

two separate but interconnected worlds that people identify with specific laws, feelings, beliefs, modes of thinking and behavior (Lambert, Kass, Piotrowski & Vodanovich, 2006). The degree to which they are central or peripheral players in either area may be known as border-crossers. The central participant shall be defined as having influence and identification. Influence suggests that the individual: has internalized the culture of the domain, has demonstrated competence in his / her responsibilities, and is linked to other central domain members (Clark, 2012). Identification occurs when individuals closely link their own identity to their domain membership. When border-crossers identify themselves with a domain, they are committed to it and want to shape it in a way that enables them to contribute and excel, which leads to a higher motivation for manage borders and domains.

Empirical Review

Syed and Nadeem (2014) examined the effects of perceived work-life balance and job satisfaction on organizational commitment among healthcare employees. It was predicted that perceived work-life balance fosters job satisfaction which leads to organizational commitment among employees in the long run. The degree of work-life balance is measured using the five statements from and eight statements from. A short version of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) was used to measure job satisfaction. Organizational commitment was measured by selecting 11 items from the work commitment index. 275 respondents completed the survey. Results showed that respondents have moderate level of perceived work-life balance, job satisfaction and commitment. Significant relationships are found among work-life balance, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. A regression analysis revealed that 37% variance in organizational commitment and job satisfaction is attributed to work-life balance.

Osman, Ibuathu and Rukangu ((2016) examined the influence of work-life balance on employee job satisfaction using Northern Rangelands trust in Isiolo County, Kenya. The study employed descriptive research design, and the population of interest for this study consisted of employees of Northern Rangelands Trust and who were specifically classified to be in top management, middle management, lower management staff and non-management. The organization has a workforce of 132 employees. The study used stratified random sampling method to ensure balanced representation in the sample and to reduce biasness in sample selection as each element was to be subjected to equal chance in selection. Questionnaire was used for data collection. The study sought to find out whether home and family responsibilities affect the work life of the respondents and how this affects job satisfaction. The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation while data presentation was done using tables. The study found that there was

relationship between work life balance and employee satisfaction. It was recommended that management should try as much as possible to build a work environment that attracts, retains, and motivates its employees so as to help them work comfortably and increase organization productivity, hence the feeling of job security.

Adikaram (2016) examined the impact of work life balance on employee job satisfaction in private sector commercial banks of Sri Lanka. The data is collected keeping in consideration of demographic factors and factors affect for job satisfaction. Factors involved are job satisfaction and work life balance with respect to Working hours, Working conditions, work life balance programs, employee intention to change of job and work pressure. Data was collected using both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected through questionnaire where secondary data was collected through past research, journals and online websites. In primary data collection, a total of 150 copies of the questionnaire were distributed among the employees of different commercial banks. The data was analyzed using SPSS, tests applied were correlation and regression. The findings suggest that work life balance had a significant impact on employee job satisfaction in private sector commercial banks of Sri Lanka.

Norton (2019) studied the relationship between work life balance and the components of organisational commitment. The study concluded that there is a positive correlation between affective commitment and perceived work life balance and the strongest correlation found to work life balance perceptions was that of worker identification with the goals of the organisation. The study showed that the individual's goals should be clear and suggested to encourage workers to align personal goals with career related goals.

Sakthivel and Jayakrishnan (2012) conducted a study on the work life balance and organisational commitment for nurses. For the study 328 nurses from public and private hospitals were selected and with the use of descriptive statistics and correlation analysis it was concluded that work life interferes with family at very high level whereas family life interfered less with work life. The study also showed that nurses experienced that better work life balance motivated them to more organisational commitment and better performance.

Atkinson (2011) conducted a study to examine the differences in work life balance, job satisfaction, organisational commitment and learning goal orientation in baby boomers and Generation Xer. The study was conducted based on the argument that the difference in the value and attitude of Gen Xer and baby boomers employees create tension and conflict

in the work place. The study found that baby boomers were most satisfied with their overall work. It was also found that job satisfaction and satisfaction with promotional job opportunities were most important in providing organisation commitment for gen Xer than for baby boomers.

Zanél (2015) examined work-life balance, job satisfaction and turnover intention amongst information technology employees. A quantitative cross-sectional survey research design was applied to a stratified random sample of 79 employees in a South African IT company. Descriptive statistics, correlations, independent t-tests and regressions were used to analyze the data. Analysis revealed that job satisfaction has a significant negative relationship with turnover intention. Furthermore, the work-home interface sub-dimensions of work-life balance have both a positive and negative relationship with job satisfaction and turnover intention. There are significant differences between the various biographical groups.

Emeka (2014) studied work-Life balance and organizational productivity in Nigeria. Contingency table was used in analyzing the data collected from the questionnaire. Again, t-test statistic was used in testing the research hypotheses. From the result, the following findings were made; that there is significant positive relationship between family responsibilities and work-life balance; that demography has significant positive impact on the work-life balance; that Culture has positive effect on the work-life balance; and that there is significant positive relationship between work-life balance and employee's productivity.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive survey design. The study population is represented by 500 employees at Radio Nigeria in Oyo State. The sample size will be done using *Taro Yamane's* formula with $n = N/(1+Ne^2)$.

Where (n) is the sample size given,
the (N) as the population size and a margin error.

$e = \text{Confidence level}$ to be set at 95 percent (an alpha level of 0.05). In this study, we used a 95 percent confidence level with a population size of 500. $n = N/(1+Ne^2) = 500/(1+500*0.05^2) = 222.222$. Approximately = 220

Data was collected from the primary source by administering questionnaire. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23.0.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Data of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Department	Engineering	29	14.5
	Administration	57	28.5
	ICT	29	14.5
	Finance/Account	52	26.0
	Programmes	28	14.0
	Procurement	5	2.5
	Total	200	100
Gender	Male	115	57.5
	Female	85	42.5
	Total	200	100
Age distribution	11-40 years	28	14.0
	36-40 years	57	28.5
	41-45 years	58	29.0
	46-50 years	57	28.5
	Total	200	100

Marital Status	Single	28	14.0
	Married	144	72.0
	Divorced	28	14.0
	Total	200	100
Educational Qualification	HND/BSc	114	57.0
	MSc/MBA	58	29.0
	Others i.e. Diploma	28	14.0
	Total	200	100
Job Rank	Middle Management	172	86.0
	Top Management	28	14.0
	Total	200	100
Work Experience	5-10 years	57	28.5
	11-15 years	114	57.0
	21 years and above	29	14.5
	Total	143	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 above shows the classification of respondents according to department, gender, age, marital status, educational qualification, job rank and work experience. The table shows the department of work for the respondents where 14.5% indicated their departments of work as Engineering and ICT respectively, 28.5% were from Administration department, 26% indicated their department as finance/account. In addition, 14% revealed their department within the organization as Programmes while 2.5% were from Procurement department. It can be inferred from the table that the majority of the respondents of this study were from the Administration department. 115 (57.5%) of the respondents are male while 85 (42.5%) are female respondents. Thus, majority of the respondents were males. Respondent who are aged below 31 – 35 years are 28 which represents 14.0% of the total population, 57 of the respondents were aged within (36 – 40) years which represents 28.5%, respondents who are aged within (41 – 45) years are 58 which represents 29.0% while 28.5% respondent of the total population were aged 46-50 years. This shows that most of the respondents are between ages 41-45 years. It is observed that 28 (14.0%) of the respondents are single, 144 (72.0%) are married while 28 (14.0%) are divorced. With the results obtained above it implies that most of the respondents are married. It is also observed that 114 (57.0%) of the respondents had HND or BSc degree in educational qualifications, 58 (29%) had MBA or Masters in any discipline on academic qualifications, while 28 (14.0%) of the respondents had other academic qualifications like Diploma, thus the majority of the respondents were HND and BSc degree holders. The table shows the distribution of the respondents on their job rank within the organization where 86% which represent 172 of the respondents indicated their job rank as middle management in the organization while 14% which represent 28 were top management. This implies that majority of the study participants were middle management level in the organization. The table showed that 57 (28.5%) of the respondents worked in the organization for 5 – 10 years, 114 (57.0%) had worked for 11 – 15 years, while 29 (14.5%) revealed that they have been actively working for 21 – 25 years in the organization. Thus, the majority of the respondents have been on the job for 11 – 15 years. This implies that most of the respondents had broad work experience with the organization.

Presentation of Data

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H_{01} : Work life balance has no significant influence on job commitment of employees at Radio Nigeria.

Table 2: A correlation table showing the relationship between Work life balance and job commitment of employees.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Work Life Balance	36.3800	9.39505	200	.319**	.000	Sig.
Job Commitment	36.5650	8.58863				

Source: Fieldwork (2023)

It is shown in the table 2 that there was significant relationship between work-life balance and job commitment among employees at Radio Nigeria ($r = .319^{**}$, $N = 200$, $P < .05$). Hence, work life balance had an influence on job commitment among the participants in the study. Null hypothesis is rejected.

This is corroborating the in-depth interview conducted that when organizations put in place a number of policies that govern the behaviour of employees in the organization and those policies are employee friendly, it is important to state that when the policies such as the closing time and opening time is favourable, employee can easily stick to the time and remain committed to their work.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : There is no significant influence of work life balance on job satisfaction of employees at Radio Nigeria.

Table 3: A correlation table showing the relationship between Work life balance and job Satisfaction of employees.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Work Life Balance	36.3800	9.39505	200	.012*	.871	Not Sig.
Job Satisfaction	40.3150	6.52754				

Source: Fieldwork (2023)

It is shown in the table 3 that there was no significant relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction among employees at Radio Nigeria ($r = .012^*$, $N = 200$, $P > .05$). Hence, work life balance had no influence on job satisfaction among the participants in the study. Null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that there is a significant influence of work life balance and job commitment among employees. In today's working environments many people have a hard time to create a balance between work and personal life. Sustainable work environment policies that will ensure better work quality by giving people more time to research and a reasonable schedule have to be accepted. One of the main struggles of the broadcasting firms is organizational commitment. They fear that after a term of investment to the employee where he/she adapts and learns the job requirements, he/she can quit the job to start another career in another firm or organization. Therefore, a good grasp of the underlying factors of organizational commitment is required for the broadcasting firms to create a desirable work environment. The findings of this study corroborates that of Oludayo et al (2018). that work leave arrangement provided by the organization, employee time out, employee social support, and dependent care initiative are predictors of employee behaviour outcomes and their ability to remain committed to their work⁴. The Nigerian working environment has been observed to be volatile, degrading, precarious and unfriendly as revealed by Mortimore and Adams (2019). Also, in the Nigerian working environment, work-life imbalances have become common occurrence and have numerous

consequences on organizations such as low productivity and growth trajectory (Igbinomwanhia et al. (2012).

These work-life imbalances can lead to the non-commitment of employees because a non-alignment exist between their roles at work and roles at home. Commitment of employees is important for achieving organizational efficiency in Nigeria's dynamic work environment⁷. Nigerian worker faces a huge task of managing domestic risks in the absence of adequate employee benefit schemes and insurance coverage. This further corroborates the findings of Boyi (2015) that organizations in this type of environment, who seek optimum performance from employees must not toy with their employees' work-life balance. This is because employees' have various roles to play; at-work, at-school and at-home and they must effectively manage these roles, in other not to lead to employee burnout. This is supported with social exchange theory that describes that mutual transactions are predicated on the costs and advantages involved in the transaction. Socio-economic transactions usually include a job arrangement. Social transfers are also reciprocal acts and can be facilitated by the care provided to its workers by a company and the presumption of reciprocity (Blau, 1964). They are defined by Settoon, Bennett and Liden (2010) as: 'Positive, beneficial behavior targeted at employees by the company and/or its representative lead to the creation of high-quality reciprocal relationships that generate expectations for employees to reciprocate in a positive way hence the commitment of such an employee can be guaranteed.

The findings also showed that there is a significant influence of work life balance and job satisfaction among employees. The findings of this study revealed that there is no significant influence between work life balance and job satisfaction of employees. The effectiveness of job satisfaction on job productivity as well as work and life balance cannot be taken for granted. Job satisfaction has known to increase productivity as an example with a 6.6% increase in productivity per hour due to a high level of job satisfaction. On the opposite side of the scale, job dissatisfaction is counter-productive and involves an employee having a general negative attitude and contentment with their job as observed in the field of work. This finding negates that of Tumen and Zeydanli (2016) that an employee having a negative outlook on the organisation that employs them, the work environment and the overall views and requirements needed (Sang, Dainty & Ison, 2009). Job dissatisfaction can be negative not only to the employer but for the employee also in relation to their physical and mental well-being. Employees who are unhappy in their job can suffer from mental issues and in extreme cases lead to depression. Work and life balance can be a primary contributor towards job dissatisfaction for employees (Sang et al.,

2009). The more and more work and hours spent in the employees place of work will lead to discontent and the employee will become aggravated and displeasure towards their job and the workplace.

Regarding retail, WLB will have a great bearing on job satisfaction and dissatisfaction but primary aspects such as wages, conditions and future prospects within the company will influence it to a greater extent. As many people are already aware, attaining job satisfaction in retail can be very difficult due to the factors mentioned with many employees leaving in search of better employment which leads to high turnovers which is the ideology know regards retail work. It further corroborates the findings of Sang, et al. (2009) that more evidence of the impact WLB can have on an employer's satisfaction in their job in a negative manner. Poor WLB policies such as working long hours led to employees being dissatisfied in their job and increased the risks involved with their own health and well-being. Management practices which were time consuming and led to greater hours worked was another factor involved along with having little opinion or voice in the decisions of the organization. Using the border theory, it is assumed that employees are seen as boundary crossers who control and navigate the worlds of employment and home, and the barriers between them in order to enter WFB. Adopting a somewhat situationalist viewpoint, Clark describes equilibrium as 'satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home with limited position tension (Clark, 2000).' From this perspective, the WFB is regarded as a condition that leads to a variety of satisfactions that are appreciated by the individual and his/her stakeholders, thereby providing the possibility to assess their actions within a situational context (Reiter, 2007). BT 's core emphasis is that boundaries and connections between work and family need to be carefully maintained to establish and sustain a desirable equilibrium or satisfaction. This negates the findings from the in-depth interview conducted on one of the personnel.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study assessed the work-life balance and employee behaviour (job commitment and satisfaction) among employees at Radio Nigeria. This study also advanced some inputs to the literature by confirming a significant influence between work life balance and job commitment, also there was no significant influence between work life balance and job satisfaction of employees in Radio Nigeria. In addition to this, the study revealed further that there are strategies put in place by organization to help foster effectiveness among employees at Radio Nigeria. This strategy includes the resumption time slated for 8 hours during the working days and 40 hours a week as well as given annual leave, study leave with pay among others.

This study offers the following recommendation:

1. Managers of these organizations should encourage their employees to fix their leave at their convenient period after performing all their work related duties. Managers of these organizations should create activities that improve employee leisure time such as sport activities.
2. Employees should be able to make the very best use of their annual leave for their personal development. While tasks that involve a high level of stress must be handled systematically in the organization.
3. Policies on welfare for families should be encouraged to care for dependents as well as the emergency unit. Also, the father of a newly born child, should also be granted paternity leave for as this period is often saddled with lot of tasks that might affect the social functioning of the man which will affect the effectiveness of the man at work.

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